

A NOTE ON THE SEPARATION OF SILICON AND TIN IN TIN-SILICA MIXTURE, WELDING BRASSES AND SILICON BRASSES BY ALKALI SULPHATE.

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Both SiO_2 and SnO_2 are susceptible to be reacted by HF and NH_4I and thus incapable of being separated by HF and NH_4I . When a mixture of SiO_2 and SnO_2 is heated with HF a mixture of SnF_4 (b. p. 705°) and SiF_4 (gas) is obtained and when heated with NH_4I , a mixture of SnI_4 (341° sublimes) and SiI_4 (b. p. 290°) is obtained, but when the mixture of SiO_2 and SnO_2 is heated with HNO_3 and HCl , baked and diluted with HCl and water. H_4SiO_4 precipitates out and Sn remains in the solution, which is treated with a strong solution (15%) of Na_2SO_4 when Sn precipitates out which on ignition yields pure SnO_2 . A mixture of pure tin (Penang) and silica (obtained from pure Norwegian metal) was obtained in solution by aqua regia, baked with HCl , finally diluted with HCl and water when H_4SiO_4 which precipitates out is filtered, washed, ignited and weighed as SiO_2 , which weight is further checked by volatilising the SiO_2 with HF . Filtrate is treated with 15% Na_2SO_4 solution, when the precipitated Sn is filtered, ignited and weighed as SnO_2 , weight of SnO_2 being checked by volatilising the same with NH_4I . Welding brasses and silicon brasses contain both silicon and tin ; both Sn and Si have been very successfully estimated by the above process. Presence of silicon increases the fluidity and tin the malleability in welding silicon brasses.

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